

MASTER THESIS

**To what extent can Signed Distance Fields benefit
destruction on Mesh Data**

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Declaration of Authorship

I, Stijn Van Coillie, declare that this thesis titled, "To what extent can Signed Distance Fields benefit destruction on Mesh Data" and the work presented are my own. I confirm that:

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“If only writing was as easy as coding.”

Stijn Van Coillie

Abstract

International Games Architecture and Design
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Master of Game Technology

To what extent can Signed Distance Fields benefit destruction on Mesh Data

By Stijn Van Coillie

To create destruction in real-time applications, video game engines depend heavily on the Voronoi approach. This method creates additional data, the level of detail depends on the number of subdivisions, and is mostly executed as a pre-process. This thesis attempts to explore a new way of applying destruction in a non-destructive way, without altering the mesh, using signed distance fields on mesh data. During this exploratory research, we started with a semi-structured interview to establish our destruction criteria for evaluation. Following this, an ideal solution was outlined, and a prototype was constructed. We then evaluated our progress with a continuous comparison by measuring and analysing the performance for every iteration. We then concluded with a visual comparison against the Voronoi fracturing method by using Q-Sort, the picture-sorting technique. The gathered data during the iteration progress concluded that our proposed method is efficient in real-time video game applications, even on low-end hardware. From the Q-sorting results we concluded that the visual outcome of our proposed signed distance field method is more visually appealing compared to the Voronoi method. While our method shows potential as a destruction method, we need to delve deeper and investigate how our approach performs on different in-game situations, assets, and hardware setups.

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List of Abbreviations

2D	Two-Dimensional
3D	Three-Dimensional
SDF	Signed Distance Field
API	Application Programming Interface
AAA	Triple A Games
VR	Virtual Reality
VFX	Visual Effects
SFX	Special Effects
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
CPU	Central Processing Unit
FPS	Frames per second

Dedicated to my love.

Chapter 1: Introduction

Destruction in games has made many improvements, from terrain destruction in *Space Invaders* (Taito, 1978) to splitting up rocks and spaceships in *Asteroids* (Atari, 1979). From destroying a simple box in *Crash Bandicoot* (Naughty Dog, 1996) to destroying the entire environment in games like *Minecraft* (Mojang Studios, 2011). This evolution has resulted in different techniques over the years.

In 2D games, one of the earliest techniques for applying destruction to the environment was using a mask texture to hide the destructible area, as seen in games such as *Worms* (Team17, 1995). This method brought a great deal of depth to a game. Players could, by blasting a projectile, apply destruction at a very controlled position. As a result, the environment changed in real-time, and characters could interact with the level in the same manner, or even fall through the destructed area.

In games like *Age of Empires* (Ensemble Studios, 1997) all the different destruction phases are predefined and rendered to a sprite sheet. Which offers high-quality visuals however the file size of the game build becomes larger. At the beginning of the 3D era, the destruction of assets was mostly shown by using particle effects. By way of illustration, there were the destroying actors in *Kileak: The DNA Imperative* (Genki, 1995) or the destroying chests in *Super Mario 64* (Nintendo, 1996).

A well-known method of displaying destruction is having two versions of the same asset. The first one is the original undamaged version, while the other is divided into different fragments beforehand. Once the player applies a force to the object you replace the original asset with the damaged one, giving the illusion of dynamic destruction. This technique is still wildly used in most in-game destruction and is becoming more advanced year after year. With more computing power comes more creative and innovative ways of designing destructible assets.

Crackdown 3 (Sumo Digital, 2019) showcased their game at Gamescom (*Gamescom*, n.d.), with a tech-demo showing their destruction done through cloud computing. Unfortunately, the presentation experienced some issues displaying this smoothly; mainly because of synchronizing and latency problems. The multiplayer game launched without this functionality. Their destruction is done by synchronized events.

Teardown (Tuxedo Labs, 2020) on the other hand handles the entire game using voxels which gives you a large destructible sandbox. However, the destruction is very cubical. Resulting in a pixelated look and feel. Nonetheless, this does show us the power of voxel-based approaches.

A tech demo from Fickle Swimming (*FickleSwimming*, 2020) shows destruction on an almost pixel perfect precision without the loss of high-quality visuals. The method shows a lot of potential towards destructible objects. Unfortunately, there are no specific details on how this was done. However, we can take this as our inspiration to explore our own destruction method.

This thesis attempts to explore a new way of applying destruction in a non-destructive way using Signed Distance Fields on Mesh Data; by answering the following research questions:

- What method can be used for this new approach?
- How efficient is this new approach?
- Is the outcome visually appealing in comparison with current methods?

During this exploratory expedition, we evaluate our progress with a continuous comparison by measuring and analysing the performance. We then conclude with a visual comparison with current methods by using Q-sort, the picture-sorting technique.

Chapter 2: Background Review

One of the earliest papers on destruction for video games was written by Parker and O'Brien (G. Parker & F. O'Brien, 2009). Their paper describes a simulation system for fracturing solid objects. The system was inspired by the co-rotational tetrahedral finite element method. Their work was used as a base by Schwartzman and Otaduy (Schwartzman et al., 2013), which evolved into one of the most used methods for destruction; a fracture algorithm that relies on the Voronoi diagram. In which the distribution of the fragments can be decided in advance, giving the developer more control on how detailed the destruction should be.

There are currently two major approaches when it comes to asset destruction within games. One approach is the Voronoi diagram method, where the 3D asset is divided into different pieces beforehand. This creates additional mesh data; meaning, it creates a minimum of two different versions of the asset. When destruction is applied to the object you activate the different fragments, giving the illusion of real-time destruction of the object. Another approach is to work with voxels to visualize your assets. In order to apply destruction to a voxel, the data structure should be modified. This results in an asset that can show visual destruction without fragmenting the initial asset. The disadvantage is that voxel assets have less artistic freedom for the reason that the detail depends on the resolution of the asset.

Creating the fracturing of a mesh is mostly a pre-process, meaning the fracturing has been applied beforehand. This can be done within the video game engine or by using external tools. A more frequently used technique for fracturing is Voronoi Fracturing (Ledoux, 2007), also called cell fracturing. It subdivides the object into different pieces by generating points inside the object, after which it computes the Voronoi cells of these points. Once these cells are known, the mesh can be split, see Figure 2.1. A well-known algorithm for this is the Bowyer-Watson method (Rebay, 1993). This method computes the points positions and their connections simultaneously.

Figure 2.1, Example of the Voronoi Fracturing technique

There are also alternative ways of fracturing a 3D object. It can be done by edge splitting, where a mesh is divided into different pieces along existing edges. Or by plane slicing, using an infinite plane to slice the mesh according to its normal. This could be done in almost any 3D editing software; such as Blender (Blender Foundation, n.d.), Autodesk 3ds Max (Autodesk, n.d.), Houdini (SideFX, n.d.) and others.

There are video game engines that provide a destruction system within the editor. In Unreal 4 (Epic Games, n.d.) it is called Chaos Destruction (Chaos Destruction, n.d.). Their system is based on the Voronoi fracturing technique and includes many different distribution techniques, such as the radial Voronoi method. This creates fractures divided in a radial way around a centre point.

There are also libraries available for destruction. One popular one is Blast (*NVIDIA Blast / NVIDIA Developer*, n.d.), from Nvidia (*NVIDIA*, n.d.). This destruction library provides a modular approach for destruction. It is also based on Voronoi fracturing. Blast provides the same variety of techniques as Chaos. The advantage of using Blast is that it can be used for any current game engine, including custom engines.

Najim (Najim et al., 2018) presented a method for fracturing 3D objects in real-time by precomputing the fracture pattern and using it to fracture the object depending on the impact. This method could only be applied for fracturing one-sided 3D meshes and resulted in low resolution fracturing. To obtain higher resolutions, a scalable tessellation was implemented. However, a much lower performance was obtained.

Another way of representing a 3D asset is by using voxels instead of mesh geometry. Voxel is derived from the word “volume” and “pixel”; they are represented in a three-dimensional space with a value (data). This value can be anything ranging from a vector to a colour. A way to make voxel assets is by using a voxel editor such as *MagicaVoxel* (*MagicaVoxel*, n.d.). Most game engines can be modified to visualize voxels. There are voxel-based engines that are fully optimized for this, such as the custom game engine from Teardown (Tuxedo Labs, 2020).

The application of destruction to a voxel-based asset is done with simple subtraction operations thanks to its data structure. For the artistic value of a voxel asset the level of detail depends on the resolution of the asset. Due to the cubical representation of voxels, the destruction has a 3D pixel art style, see Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2, Example of a Voxel asset, by artist Burç Tuncer

Voxels can also be represented as a Signed Distance Field (SDF). The field represents the 3D texture that contains each sample of the SDF. The distance is the closest distance to the surface of the mesh. And the sign determines whether the sample is inside the mesh or not. To render out an SDF, we use a method called Raymarching. John C. Hart (Hart, 1996) suggests the Sphere Tracing technique to render out our SDF. This technique uses marching along a ray towards its first intersection. The step of this ray is determined by the minimum distance within the SDF, see Figure 2.3. With the point of intersection, we can calculate the normal and shade the inside as we would with traditional renders.

Instead of using Raymarching to visualize our SDF, there is also the possibility to generate a triangle mesh. This technique is called Marching cubes, introduced by William E. Lorensen and Harvey E. Cline (Lorensen & Cline, 1987). It is an algorithm that creates a triangle model according to the values of the data. However, Marching Cubes models have the tendency to look visually less detailed and smooths out the surface, making sharp characteristics difficult to visualize.

Figure 2.3, Example of Sphere Tracing

Table 2.1 lists all the mentioned techniques and methods with a brief definition, their pros and their cons. All methods have their own purpose with advantages and disadvantages according to the situation.

Method	Description	Pros	Cons
Edge Splitting	Splits the mesh along the existing edge of the mesh.	Fast operation and creates minimal additional data.	Limited to the level of detail of the mesh. The result is a number of non-solid meshes.
Plane Slicing	An infinite plane determines the slicing of the mesh, according to the transform and normal of the plane.	Fast operation on convex meshes.	The fracturing always results in two pieces, perfectly along a normal of the plane.
Voronoi Fracturing	A 3D Voronoi Diagram subdivides the mesh along the border of its cells.	Wide variety of Voronoi techniques. For instance, Radial and Brick Voronoi.	Fracturing is predefined and limited to the number of cell divisions. Additionally, it creates extra mesh data.
Voxels	A volumetric data structure to represent an asset.	Efficiently fast for Boolean operations and can contain additional data.	Voxels have a cubical representation and often take up more memory since you need a lot of data to get a certain level of detail.
Signed Distance Fields	A grid in which each sample holds the closest distance to the surface of an object, mostly represented as a 2D/3D texture.	Efficiently fast for Boolean operations.	It is an approximation of the asset. The higher the level of detail, the more data is needed.
Marching Cubes	An algorithm to construct a polygonal mesh from a voxel data structure.	Generates a triangle mesh from a voxel data structure.	It is an approximation of the original asset. Sharp features are lost because of the linear interpolation. Increasing the voxel resolution will reduce the artifacts, however it will never remove them.

Table 2.1, Methods or techniques to represent destruction in video games

In the second quarter of 2020, a developer by the name of Fickle Swimming released a small tech demo video of applying destruction in a very precise way on a large static mesh (*FickleSwimming, 2020*). The destruction, which was on a very high-quality asset, was almost pixel perfect. The method for the precise destruction was not provided by Swimming. In the comment section of Reddit (*Reddit, 2020*) Swimming gave a brief description regarding the steps of this tech demo; describing that this approach of destruction combines voxel destruction with traditional 3D geometry.

We propose to investigate our own method to explore a non-destructive way for applying destruction on a mesh. In theory we would render out the destructed parts with a voxel approach and render the mesh itself with a traditional shader approach. To achieve this,

we create a Signed Distance Field (SDF) of the asset, described by Bastian Kraye and Stefan Muller (Kraye & Müller, 2019), and use it as a 3D texture. Each pixel gives us the nearest distance to the closest surface. Resulting in the possibility to calculate fast operations without modifying the mesh data. It allows us to perform all destruction in a pixel-perfect matter on the SDF. The rendering of the mesh itself can be done in the traditional way with one modification, we sample from the 3D texture and discard the fragments where there is destruction. We are then left with holes inside the asset, similar to the old-school techniques which were used on games such as Worms or Tanks. To finalize our method, we need to visualize the inside. For this we use the Raymarching technique, explained by John C. Hart (Hart, 1996). Where the distance function is the subtraction operation of our Signed Distance Fields.

Chapter 3: Methodology

For the exploratory approach, also called the ground theory approach (*Designing a Research Project*, 2012) we started our journey by establishing a baseline. Next, we searched and explored our hypothesis in an iterative process; researching familiar and unfamiliar areas to improve our approach. Every improved iteration will be compared to the previous method and will be set as the new baseline if significant improvements are noticed. The iterative process should happen for every new step that has been explored. For this, a criterion must be set.

Referring to Joris van Gestel's paper (van Gestel, 2011), we established that a destruction method should have five criteria for evaluation: performance, control, ease of use, ease of integration and quality. A semi-structured interview was conducted to support this argument. Participants from different backgrounds and occupations were interviewed to better understand the criteria for destruction. Results showed that participants found performance and quality the most important criteria. Motivating our argument to focus on efficiency and visual appearance during the study.

Therefore, we will be evaluating our progress with a continuous comparison of the performance by measuring and analysing the iterations. The goal would be to push the approach to a real-time destruction method and to evaluate our result with a visual comparison. The visual aid will help establish if the found method is also visually pleasing and if it has potential to be used to apply destruction within video games.

3.1 Baseline

Unity (*Unity*, n.d.) was used for the development part to construct the baseline for our method. Our expertise lies within the Unity video game engine, which is why we used it. However, this method can be constructed in any 3D video game engine that supports compute shaders; for instance, the Unreal Engine (Epic Games, n.d.) or the CryEngine (*CryEngine*, n.d.).

3.1.1 Set-up

A Signed Distance Field was generated from our mesh, using the proposed method by Bastian Kraye and Stefan Müller (Kraye & Müller, 2019). Their method, to calculate the SDF, has been entirely done on the GPU, allowing to perform efficiently in parallel. For our purpose generating the SDF was done offline, in the editor. It gave us the possibility to

expand it in case we needed it at compile time or runtime. According to the paper it runs a lot faster than CPU methods. The algorithm is split into a distance method and a method to compute the sign.

To calculate the distance, they used the distance transform method by Felzenszwalb (Felzenszwalb & Huttenlocher, 2012). A more practical example of this implementation was developed by Inigo Quiles (Quilez, n.d.). The method gives us the shortest distance to the nearest surface position. However, it does not give us the information whether we are inside or outside the mesh. To fix this, the second part of the algorithm comes into play.

To determine the sign of the distance we made use of the Möller–Trumbore intersection algorithm (Mm & Trumbore, 1997), named after its inventors Tomas Möller and Ben Trumbore. We cast a ray and counted how many intersections were happening with the mesh triangles. If the outcome was even, then the sign was positive. In case of an uneven intersection, we had a negative sign. To be able to access this information later, we then wrote all this data onto a 3D texture.

3.1.2 Destruction method

If we wanted to apply damage to our asset, we needed to create an extra SDF which stored our damage information. The damage could either be applied at an exact point or by using a ray. In the case of the latter, we had to calculate our point of impact. This was done by using the sphere tracing technique (1.1), where f is the given signed distance field, r the direction and D maximum distance.

Initialize $t = 0$ and $d = 0$ (1.1)

While $t < D$

Let $d = f(r * t)$

If $d < \epsilon$ then return t --- intersection

Increment $t = t + d$

Return \emptyset --- no intersection

If the outcome was a no-hit intersection, we could assume we did not have to apply damage to the SDF since there was no direct impact. If we did have a point of impact; we had to update our destruction SDF. In the case of a sphere subtraction, we could loop over every position in our SDF and calculate the distance to the point of impact (1.2), subtracting the radius of our sphere (1.3). The result gave us the correct signed distance.

If the distance was smaller than the previous distance, we updated our 3D texture with the new value (1.4).

Given point of impact poi and previous distance pd

$$d = \text{distance}(p, poi) \quad (1.2)$$

$$d = d - r \quad (1.3)$$

$$pd = \min(pd, d) \quad (1.4)$$

3.1.3 Rendering the asset

We started by finding out if our fragment is in the damaged part of our asset. To determine this, we sampled from our destruction SDF by converting our position from object space to SDF's space (1.5), where s is the maximum size of the asset and op is the object's position.

$$ss = (op / s + 1.0) * 0.5 \quad (1.5)$$

If our distance was smaller or equal to zero, we assumed that the fragment was located in the destructed area of our asset. We then rendered out this fragment with the ray marching rendering technique, also known as volume ray casting. To calculate the distance, we used the subtraction operation (1.6), where $d1$ is the distance sampled from our mesh's SDF, see 3.1.1. And $d2$ is the distance sampled from our destruction SDF.

$$d = \max(-d2, d1) \quad (1.6)$$

We spoke of a miss when the outcome of the ray marching determined that there was no volume to render. This meant there was a hole in the mesh and the fragment could be discarded or clipped. If the fragment was not in the destructed area, we rendered the fragment using the traditional way of rendering a 3D model. In our example this was equal to a simple lit shader which rendered out a colour. However, in theory any shader could be used. For the shading part we went with the Lambertian method for both rendering techniques. Even though we were using two different rendering techniques, they were both done in one draw call.

3.2 Data Gathering

The data gathered during the iteration needed to provide an answer to the efficiency of the destruction method. Our focus laid on exploring different possibilities to improve the proposed method in Section 3.1.2. During this process each iteration collected data to compare if there were significant improvements. The goal was to achieve an as optimal method as possible within the time constrains. The final result was then compared visually to the Voronoi fracturing method. The execution order of the methods is visualized in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1, Overview of used methods

3.2.1 Interview

An interview was conducted to establish the criterion for destruction. Based upon the Game Research Methods book, Table 1. *Parts of an interview guide* (Drachten et al., 2018), we chose a semi-structured interview. This interview format was best suited for a two-way communication which allowed room to discuss a certain topic more in-depth. The semi-structured interview consisted of five questions with numerous predefined follow-up questions, see appendix A.1. These questions were more intended to guide the conversation and stimulate the purpose of the conducted interview.

3.2.2 Continuous comparison

The most used technique for exploratory research is called continuous comparison, which is the process of comparing each finding with a previously established approach. We investigated whether the new finding had a significant improvement over the compared version, using the Welch's t-test (Moser & Stevens, 1992). The Welch's t-test compares two sample groups to test out the hypothesis that the two groups have equal means. To create the samples, we executed our findings fifty times on each asset. Each sample gets executed by casting a ray to the centre of the asset, executing our destruction method described in Section 3.1.2. After this process we reset the asset to its original state, so we can continue the next sample with the same conditions.

The 3D objects used to test out our new findings were three primitives and one complex mesh, see Figure 3.2. These objects were tested to see if there was a difference in performance between these objects and if there were any irregularities. All the objects had the same set-up. This included texture size, impact point and radius of damage.

Figure 3.2, Assets used during the continuous comparison study, available in Appendix A.5

The focus during each iteration lies mainly on improving and measuring the performance of applying the destruction method, described in Section 3.1.2. We do not focus on the rendering of the asset, since we are already using a well-established method and improving on this would be a topic on its own. However, this does not mean we will compromise the visual aspect for an even better performance. No changes should be made to the rendering part, described in Section 3.1.3. The steps of the method are visualized in Figure 3.3, where the bold outline is the step we are measuring.

Note. Condition tests if we need to apply destruction.

Figure 3.3, Flow of the entire destruction method.

3.2.3 Visual comparison

The result developed during the iterations, see Section 4.2, was visually compared to the Voronoi fracturing method, with a focus on the damaged area. For this, 16 statements were provided in video format. This way all participants saw the exact same destructions. We tested our visual comparison on four different objects, see Figure 3.2. We used two different methods on two different levels of detail for each object, ending up with a total of 16 statements for our Q-sorting. The level of detail for our proposed method is the resolution of our signed distance fields, which are $64px^3$ and $128px^3$. We are using the Chaos Destruction system limitations for the Voronoi fracturing as a reference for our fracturing count, and is therefore limited to 1000 fractures. The higher level of detail is double that amount. The fractured objects can be found at Appendix A.5.

For the signed distance field subtraction function, see Section 3.1.2, we implemented three different ways of subtraction to see if certain visual subtractions have a different outcome in the Q-sorting study. We applied a sphere function (1.7), an infinite line function that presents a smooth destruction (1.8) and a function for a random rotated cube which visualizes a fractured look (1.9). All these functions are very performant, although performance is not the focus for the visual comparison study.

Given point of impact poi and ray direction rd

$$d = \text{distance}(p, poi) - r \quad (1.7)$$

$$p = p - poi \quad (1.8)$$

$$h = \text{saturate}(\text{dot}(p, rd) / \text{dot}(rd, rd))$$

$$d = \text{length}(p - rd * h) - r$$

$$\begin{aligned}
p &= \text{mul}(\text{rotate}(\text{randomUnit}), p) && (1.9) \\
p &= \text{abs}(p) - r \\
d &= \text{length}(\text{max}(p,0) + \text{min}(\text{max}(p.x, \text{max}(p.y,p.z)),0))
\end{aligned}$$

The recording of the statements happened in the same conditions for all assets. The asset gets destroyed in an empty scene with a ground plane, both rendered by the Lambertian method, as mentioned in Section 3.1.3. With a destruction executed by a forward destruction, followed by a descending diagonal destruction from left to right. Each asset is recorded separately for a duration of around six seconds, see Appendix A.2 for the video results, creating short to the point statements for the participants.

Using the convenience sampling, from the non-probability sampling technique (Barratt & Shantikumar, 2018), a total of 14 participants were used to sort these results according to their visual appeal. We chose to go with a non-probability approach because it is recommended for exploratory research and because all participants have a background in game development; thus, some individuals have no chance of being selected.

The Q-sort methodology was used for the qualitative judgements of the participants and for having the option of a quantitative analyse. The Q-sort methodology researched and proposed by Stephenson (Stephenson, 1984), focuses on understanding the subjectivity of the individual. Q-sort requires a participant to arrange a set of predetermined statements; in this case visuals of the destruction applied on different assets with different methods. Participants were instructed to sort all 16 statements according to its destruction satisfaction in a video game context. The sorting happens in three ranking orders. The first being the visually least satisfied category. Second, the neutral feeling towards the visuals. Lastly, the visually satisfied category. All the sorting happens in a normal or bell-shaped grid, giving the possibility to have tied ranks, for an example see Appendix 3.1. Afterwards, when the participant completed the Q-sorting we asked why certain statements were more satisfying and what they did not like about the least satisfied statements.

3.3 Limitations of the Research

The iterations were mainly focused on the performance of the method. Focusing on all five criteria was not possible within the time constraints. The goal was to find the most optimal way of applying damage to an asset. Other aspects of a destruction method were

discarded, such as physics, rendering, particles, VFX, SFX, and others. With additional time, improvements could have been made on the current implementation.

The method that has been proposed has been prototyped and tested inside Unity, the video game engine. However, this method could be implemented into any video game engine that supports compute shaders. Since we are using a commercial video game engine, we need to be aware of overhead. Even though we are measuring a specific functionality there will always be unexpected costs. To reduce this we simplified the scene, as a result there is nothing complex that would produce more overhead.

3.4 Ethical Considerations

For the visual comparison study, participants were notified at the beginning of the test that their answers will be anonymous. We only requested the participants to share their results of the Q-sorting and for the additional remarks at the end. The gathered information will be handled according to the General Data Protection Regulation.

Participants of the Q methodology test consisted largely out of university students in majors focusing on game development. This does not pose a big issue for our study, since our research is meant for the video game industry. It does, however, have a big impact on the average age of the participant and their industry experience. Unfortunately, within this study there is no alternative since this test must be executed manually and due to time constrains it is unfeasible to look for a different sampling group. Another factor we had to keep in mind when doing this study with industry related participants is their occupational deformity. To minimize this, we focussed on diversity (interests, skills and age) within the participants.

Chapter 4: Data and Results

In this section, we present the results following a similar structure as mentioned in Section 3.2. The study started out with a semi-structured interview to establish the criterion of our destruction. Followed by a continuous comparison study, with a focus on improving the performance. The results of the iteration cycle were then evaluated by the Q-sort methodology, presented in Section 3.2.3.

All iterations were performed with the same PC; Intel® Core™ i5-8300H CPU @ 2.30Ghz, 16 GB DDR4 DRAM 3200Mhz and Nvidia GeForce GTX 1050 T, in a standalone build with no background activities. The performance benchmarks were collected in milliseconds and ticks. Every iteration was tested on all four assets, see Section 3.2, with a test sample count of 50. All assets had a signed distance field texture of 64 px³ and a signed distance field destruction texture of 64px³ and 128px³. The destruction texture was modified for all assets with the same variables.

4.1 Interview

A total of five interviews were conducted to confirm if the criteria provided by Joris van Gestel (van Gestel, 2011) were indeed a correct finding. The five keywords, performance, control, ease of use, ease of integration and quality, were for every participant the main focus. Among the participants, the developers found that another very important aspect was the ability to iterate quickly. In their opinion this factor was missing in current available methods for destruction. All participants also mentioned that performance and quality have a more important notice when using a method. Mainly because this has a direct influence on the end user, in this case the player. All other criteria are secondary and can be improved with time. When asked how they approached destruction for in-game assets, Voronoi fracturing was the most known approach. The tools they used varied from in-engine tools to third party tools, such as Houdini. Participants noted that context played a big part in this.

4.2 Iterations

For our method to be perceived as a real-time destruction, we needed to set a minimum performance requirement. For our project we set out to reach 60 FPS. Although, this should be higher considering we tested our method in an isolated situation. In this context, it did suffice for our exploration. We used milliseconds and ticks to measure the performance for our continuous comparison study. Ticks are the smallest unit of time

with which we can measure, giving us the most precise data. We set our benchmark to 16.6 milliseconds for our iteration process, since one frame takes about 16.6 milliseconds.

4.2.1 Baseline

A baseline, or our minimum viable product, was established to start off our iteration study, Section 3.1. It was the starting point to improve, measure, and compare our future findings. Our method was entirely executed on the CPU, with the exception of the initial set-up. The baseline had the ability to collect data from each asset, under the same conditions. This data gathering method did not change during our iteration process.

A build of the current iteration iterates over every asset, applies identical damage and exports this data to a CSV file.

Asset	S	R	min	max	MS
Sphere	50	64 ³	69.672	75.273	70.349 ± 0.93
Sphere	50	128 ³	658.158	680.371	662.928 ± 3.83
Cube	50	64 ³	69.588	70.928	69.940 ± 0.28
Cube	50	128 ³	657.490	796.942	665.698 ± 19.19
Capsule	50	64 ³	69.678	74.160	70.207 ± 0.84
Capsule	50	128 ³	653.237	668.414	661.596 ± 3.28
Mesh	50	64 ³	69.541	75.615	70.43 ± 1.18
Mesh	50	128 ³	655.841	685.128	661.106 ± 4.75

Table 4.1, Performance results from the baseline Section 4.2.1; number of samples; resolution of the SDF in pixels; minimum and maximum in milliseconds; and the mean milliseconds (\pm standard deviation).

Figure 4.1, Visualization of performance results from the baseline for each asset and resolution.

The data collection of our baseline has been executed along the guidelines from Section 3.2.2. Table 4.1 gives a summary of our minimum viable product performance result and is visualized by Figure 4.1 compared to our benchmark. These results were the foundation of our iteration process. A complete overview of these results can be found in Appendix A.3.

4.2.2 Compute Shader

Compute shaders are programs that run on the GPU. They are not part of the regular rendering pipeline. Instead, they are used for processing big data, algorithms, among others. For example, in Section 2.1.1 the paper from Bastian Krayer and Stefan Müller (Krayer & Müller, 2019) mentioned that they perceived significant improvements by performing the signed distance field algorithm on the GPU.

We converted our destruction method, seen in Section 3.1.2, into a compute shader. The way we executed our algorithm remained the same. However, we did change the way we obtained our 3D pixel position, since we were not using a nested for loop anymore. We converted our *id* from our compute shader into a 3D position (5.1).

$$\begin{aligned}
 xQ &= id / s & (5.1) \\
 yQ &= xQ / s \\
 zQ &= yQ \% s \\
 &return uint3(id \% s, xQ \% s, yQ \% s)
 \end{aligned}$$

Asset	N	R	min	max	MS	p-Value
Sphere	50	64 ³	6.249	7.351	6.529 ± 0.16	<0.001
Sphere	50	128 ³	59.632	62.977	60.399 ± 0.61	<0.001
Cube	50	64 ³	6.454	10.426	7.072 ± 0.8	<0.001
Cube	50	128 ³	59.176	65.259	60.075 ± 0.86	<0.001
Capsule	50	64 ³	6.151	7.075	6.540 ± 0.16	<0.001
Capsule	50	128 ³	59.679	65.486	60.743 ± 0.95	<0.001
Mesh	50	64 ³	6.442	8.498	6.811 ± 0.27	<0.001
Mesh	50	128 ³	59.253	64.997	60.84 ± 1.12	<0.001

Table 4.2, Performance results from the compute shader Section 4.2.2; number of samples; resolution of the SDF in pixels; minimum and maximum in milliseconds; mean milliseconds (±standard deviation); and the p-value.

Figure 4.2, Visualization of performance results from the baseline versus the compute shader Section 4.2.2 for each asset and resolution.

Table 4.2 summarizes the performance results from the compute shader in Section 4.2.2. To compare the results with our baseline, a visualization has been made in Figure 4.2. A complete overview of these results can be found in Appendix A.3.

4.2.3 Threads

Threads define how many groups can be executed when the compute shader has been dispatched (*Threads*, n.d.). Since we used DirectX 11 (*Direct3D 11 Graphics*, n.d.) for our project it is good to know that the maximum number of threads in a group ($X \times Y \times Z$) is limited to 1024 (*Compute Shader Overview*, n.d.).

Our compute shader in Section 3.5.2 was running on 256 threads (5.2) in one dimension.

$$[\text{numthreads}(256,1,1)] \tag{5.2}$$

We performed our experiment with three different number of threads, 512 threads (5.3), 1024 threads (5.4) in one dimension and 32 threads across two dimensions (5.5).

$$[\text{numthreads}(512,1,1)] \tag{5.3}$$

$$[\text{numthreads}(1024,1,1)] \tag{5.4}$$

$$[\text{numthreads}(32,32,1)] \tag{5.5}$$

The following results are from the threads 5.3 Section 4.2.3, i.e., 512 threads in one dimension. A complete overview of these results can be found in Appendix A.4.3.

Asset	S	R	min	max	MS	p-Value
Sphere	50	64 ³	6.195	6.694	6.498 ± 0.09	0.244
Sphere	50	128 ³	59.724	61.668	60.692 ± 0.42	0.006
Cube	50	64 ³	6.448	9.279	6.792 ± 0.37	0.028
Cube	50	128 ³	59.262	64.445	60.304 ± 0.91	0.203
Capsule	50	64 ³	6.206	6.850	6.473 ± 0.10	0.017
Capsule	50	128 ³	59.114	61.976	60.563 ± 0.61	0.266
Mesh	50	64 ³	6.574	9.285	6.876 ± 0.52	0.434
Mesh	50	128 ³	59.191	61.751	60.461 ± 0.52	0.034

Table 4.3, Performance results from the threads 5.3 Section 4.2.3; number of samples; resolution of the SDF in pixels; minimum and maximum in milliseconds; mean milliseconds (\pm standard deviation); and the p-value.

Figure 4.3, Visualization of performance results from the baseline versus the threads 5.3 Section 4.2.3 for each asset and resolution.

Table 4.3 summarizes the performance results from the threads 5.3 Section 4.2.3. To compare the results with our baseline, a visualization has been made in Figure 4.3.

The following results are from the threads 5.4 Section 4.2.3, i.e., 1024 threads in one dimension. A complete overview of these results can be found in Appendix A.3.

Asset	S	R	min	max	MS	p-Value
Sphere	50	64 ³	6.352	6.691	6.537 ± 0.09	0.781
Sphere	50	128 ³	59.291	62.014	60.334 ± 0.52	0.572
Cube	50	64 ³	6.609	9.235	6.833 ± 0.36	0.059
Cube	50	128 ³	59.171	61.978	60.066 ± 0.54	0.952
Capsule	50	64 ³	6.277	7,230	6.457 ± 0.11	0.004
Capsule	50	128 ³	59.693	68.378	60.905 ± 1.35	0.491
Mesh	50	64 ³	6.588	8.757	6.835 ± 0.29	0.674
Mesh	50	128 ³	59.106	61.041	59.904 ± 0.47	<0.001

Table 4.4, Performance results from the threads 5.4 Section 4.2.3; number of samples; resolution of the SDF in pixels; minimum and maximum in milliseconds; mean milliseconds (\pm standard deviation); and the p-value.

Figure 4.4, Visualization of performance results from the baseline versus the threads 5.4 Section 4.2.3 for each asset and resolution.

Table 4.4 summarizes the performance results from the threads 5.4 Section 4.2.3. To compare the results with our baseline, a visualization has been made in Figure 4.4.

The following results are from the threads 5.5 Section 4.2.3, i.e., 32 threads in two dimensions. A complete overview of these results can be found in Appendix A.3.

Asset	S	R	min	max	MS	p-Value
Sphere	50	64 ³	6,537.446	6,606.313	6,574.324 ± 20.8	<0.001
Sphere	50	128 ³	58.812	62.197	59.943 ± 0.75	0.001
Cube	50	64 ³	6,542.113	6,592.184	6,583.906 ± 13.79	<0.001
Cube	50	128 ³	58.914	63.764	59.870 ± 0.78	0.220
Capsule	50	64 ³	5,997.873	6,592.388	6,560.747 ± 115.59	<0.001
Capsule	50	128 ³	58.835	63.842	59.755 ± 0.76	<0.001
Mesh	50	64 ³	5,998.259	6,605.810	6,577.035 ± 82.83	<0.001
Mesh	50	128 ³	58.901	61.919	59.664 ± 0.50	<0.001

Table 4.5, Performance results from the threads 5.5 Section 4.2.3; number of samples; resolution of the SDF in pixels; minimum and maximum in milliseconds; mean milliseconds (\pm standard deviation); and the p-value.

Figure 4.5, Visualization of performance results from the baseline versus the threads 5.5 Section 4.2.3 for each asset and resolution.

Table 4.5 summarizes the performance results from the threads 5.5 Section 4.2.3. To compare the results with our baseline, a visualization has been made in Figure 4.5.

4.2.4 Texture Format

We needed to define a texture format, when creating our SDF 3D texture. It defined how the texture asset should store its data. Unity provides many texture formats (*TextureFormat - Unity*, n.d.). For our purpose, the texture format had to support a signed float value. Initially, we used an RGBAFloat Texture format since we were using the RGB

channels to store the normal vector and the alpha channel to store the signed distance value. Another option was to calculate the normal vector in our Sphere Tracing algorithm, see Section 3.1.3. Finally, we changed our SDF to an RFloat texture format. It stores only our signed distance value, since we only need a single channel for this.

Asset	S	R	min	max	MS	p-Value
Sphere	50	64 ³	1.857	2.146	1.976 ± 0.08	<0.001
Sphere	50	128 ³	10.022	10.961	10.362 ± 0.15	<0.001
Cube	50	64 ³	2.285	5.751	2.652 ± 0.58	<0.001
Cube	50	128 ³	10.196	12.978	11.007 ± 0.59	<0.001
Capsule	50	64 ³	2.275	4.388	2.555 ± 0.29	<0.001
Capsule	50	128 ³	10.143	11.783	10.555 ± 0.41	<0.001
Mesh	50	64 ³	1.950	2.397	2.16 ± 0.12	<0.001
Mesh	50	128 ³	10.468	12.406	10.935 ± 0.44	<0.001

Table 4.6, Performance results from the texture format Section 4.2.4; number of samples; resolution of the SDF in pixels; minimum and maximum in milliseconds; mean milliseconds (\pm standard deviation); and the p-value.

Figure 4.6, Visualization of performance results from the baseline versus the texture format Section 4.2.4 for each asset and resolution.

Table 4.6 summarizes the performance results from the texture format Section 4.2.4. To compare the results with our baseline, a visualization has been made in Figure 4.6. A complete overview of these results can be found in Appendix A.3.

4.2.5 Sphere Tracing

In Section 3.5.2 we converted our destruction method to a compute shader. In this iteration we did the same for our Sphere Tracing algorithm. The structure of the algorithm stayed the same, as seen in Section 3.1.2. We only changed the maximum loop count to 512 for the number of threads (5.6). We executed a total of 512 hit checks, where the distance of the position was calculated by multiplying the id by s , the minimum step (5.7).

$$[numthreads(512,1,1)] \quad (5.6)$$

$$d = id.x * s \quad (5.7)$$

Asset	S	R	min	max	MS	p-Value
Sphere	50	64 ³	1.865	2.182	1.986 ± 0.08	0.512
Sphere	50	128 ³	9.949	10.919	10.269 ± 0.16	0.003
Cube	50	64 ³	2.189	6.403	2.694 ± 0.70	0.748
Cube	50	128 ³	9.982	12.758	10.793 ± 0.56	0.066
Capsule	50	64 ³	2.294	4.402	2.580 ± 0.28	0.669
Capsule	50	128 ³	9.924	11.480	10.316 ± 0.28	<0.001
Mesh	50	64 ³	1.942	2.558	2.130 ± 0.13	0.249
Mesh	50	128 ³	10.364	12.412	10.908 ± 0.48	0.767

Table 4.7, Performance results from the sphere tracing Section 4.2.5; number of samples; resolution of the SDF in pixels; minimum and maximum in milliseconds; mean milliseconds (\pm standard deviation); and the p-value.

Figure 4.7, Visualization of performance results from the baseline versus the sphere tracing Section 4.2.5 for each asset and resolution.

Table 4.7 summarizes the performance results from the sphere tracing Section 4.2.5. To compare the results with our baseline, a visualization has been made in Figure 4.7. A complete overview of these results can be found in Appendix A.3.

4.2.6 End result

The following figures represent the result of the continuous comparison study and the process it took for each iteration. For every iteration, we performed the same data gathering method, under the same conditions. Each step is comprised of an overview of the sample size, resolution, minimum milliseconds, maximum milliseconds, and the mean. A Welch T-Test result table was used to compare the data with the previous step. A complete overview of the data gathering process can be found in Section 3.2.2. These results allow assumptions on how the method performed.

Figure 4.8, Visualization of performance results from the final iteration for each asset and resolution.

Figure 4.9, Visualization of the mean performance result per iteration; and per level of detail.

Figure 4.8 visualizes the performance results from the final iteration compared to our benchmark of 16.6 milliseconds. Figure 4.9 visualizes the development of each iteration expressed in the mean performance results of that iteration for both levels of detail, i.e., 64px³ and 128px³. A complete result of all the data can be found in Appendix A.3. The source code of the prototype can be found in Appendix A.6.

4.2.7 Low-end Performance Test

Although the iteration study is not focused on low-end devices, we did execute an initial test to analyse the performance. The aim was to evaluate if our proposed method would also be valid for low-end devices; and to see how it compared to our end result mentioned in Section 4.2.6. For our low-end performance test, we used an Intel® Core™ i7-3610QM CPU @ 2.30Ghz, 8 GB DDR3 DRAM and Nvidia GeForce GT 650M. We executed our data gathering in the same conditions as mentioned in Section 4.2.2, i.e., in a standalone build with no background activities. According to the latest hardware survey from Steam (*Steam Hardware & Software Survey*, n.d.), this placed our hardware setup in the low-range category, while our hardware setup described in Section 4 is considered a mid-range setup.

Figure 4.10, Visualization of performance results from the baseline versus the low-end results.

Figure 4.10 visualizes the performance results from the low-end setup compared to our baseline. A complete overview of the data gathered during the low-end performance test can be found in Appendix A.3.

4.3 Visual Comparison

A total of 16 statements were provided for the visual comparison, video statements are available in Appendix A.4. The recordings of each statement all happened in the same conditions. The asset gets destroyed in an empty scene with a ground plane, both of which were rendered by the Lambertian method. The details of this progress can be found in Section 3.2.3.

ID	Asset	Level of detail	Method
1	Capsule	2000f	Voronoi
2	Capsule	1000f	Voronoi
3	Capsule	128px ³	SDF - 1.9
4	Capsule	64px ³	SDF - 1.9
5	Cube	2000f	Voronoi
6	Cube	1000f	Voronoi
7	Cube	128px ³	SDF - 1.8
8	Cube	64px ³	SDF - 1.9
9	Rock	2000f	Voronoi
10	Rock	1000f	Voronoi
11	Rock	128px ³	SDF - 1.8
12	Rock	64px ³	SDF - 1.7
13	Sphere	2000f	Voronoi
14	Sphere	1000f	Voronoi
15	Sphere	128px ³	SDF - 1.8

16 Sphere 64px³ SDF – 1.7

Table 4.8, Overview of the statements used for the Q-sorting, each statement assigned with an ID; Asset; Level of detail in fractures or px³; and the method used for destruction.

For each method we created an equal number of statements, resulting in eight statements for the Voronoi method and eight statements for the Signed Distance Field approach. Additionally, an equal distribution occurred for the level of detail. Only the SDF subtraction function has an unequal distribution. We divided the three subtraction functions, see Section 3.2.3, among the eight SDF statements. Resulting in two sphere functions, three infinite line functions and three random rotating cube functions. It gave some diversity among the assets. A summary has been made in Table 4.8 and the assets used for this study can found at Appendix A.5.

4.3.1 Results

The following table and figures represent the most relevant observations from the Visual Comparison study. We used the Q-Sort method, also called Q-Methodology, to evaluate our study, described in Section 3.2.3. All participants completed the test successfully, as a result no data had to be discarded. A complete overview of this data can be found at Appendix A.2.

ID	min	max	score	SD
1	0	1	-2	1.30
2	2	1	-8	1.68
3*	1	1	8	1.35
4*	0	2	9	1.49
5	0	1	7	1.35
6	0	1	1	1.39
7*	3	0	-10	1.75
8*	1	1	8	1.35
9	2	0	-7	1.55
10	0	0	<i>-13</i>	<i>1.03</i>
11*	1	1	7	1.88
12*	0	3	5	1.72
13	0	2	13	1.33
14	1	0	-10	1.22
15*	1	0	-6	1.50
16*	2	0	-2	1.46

Note. N = 14; values in bold are maximums; values in italic are minimums.

Table 4.9, Summary of the Q-sorting results for each statement; * indicates our own method; basic statistics from the Q-sort study; and the standard deviation.

Figure 4.11, Visualization of the score for each id; and the mean.

Figure 4.12, Visualization of the mean score for each subtraction function.

Table 4.9 summarizes the Q-Sort results, supported by the score, minimum count, maximum count, and standard deviation. To compare the results with each statement a visualization has been made in Figure 4.11, together with the mean of both compared methods. To isolate which subtraction function had the most preference, a visualisation was made in Figure 4.12.

4.3.2 Remarks

No negative remarks were made towards the Q-sorting study, all participants found the instruction clear and easy to perform. Regarding the statements, the most prominent remark was that sometimes it was hard to tell the difference between two statements was. This remark was always regarding the level of detail of the Signed Distance Field statements. The second reoccurring remark was that physics and debris would have made

to the destruction more impressive, even though they knew that was not part of the study. Another notable mention was a suggestion to test out the destruction on different kinds of materials and to observe if there is any tearing on the destroyed parts.

Chapter 5: Discussion of Data and Results

In the previous chapter we presented our data gathered during the interview, the iteration, and the visual comparison study. The results from the iteration study, see Section 4.2, include a summary of the performance results for each iteration, a Welch's T-Test p-Value, Figure 4.8 visualizing the end result, an overview of each iteration in Figure 4.9 and a visualization at Figure 4.10 of the performance results on a low-end hardware setup. The results from the visual comparison study, see Section 4.3, include an overview of the statements in Table 4.8, a summary of the Q-Sorting results for each statement in Table 4.9 and a visualization of the mean score for each subtraction function.

5.1 Interview

During the interview there were a few indications that the criteria, see Section 4.1, was missing a keyword, and that not all keywords had equal weight. The developers among the participants found that the ability to iterate quickly was missing from this list. Since quick iteration would improve the development process, it is a valid point to include this keyword. All participants agreed that performance and quality are of more importance compared to the rest. This indicated that not all keywords should have an equal weight in the criteria. Further research would be needed to establish a standardized method to evaluate a destruction method.

5.2 Iterations

Our study started off by setting a baseline, see Section 4.2.1. The performance results of this baseline displayed in Table 4.1 and Figure 4.1 showed that the results were still far from our minimum performance requirement, set in Section 4.2. Calculating our signed distance field through a compute shader increased our performance, as mentioned in Section 3.1.1, and even pushed our $64px^3$ destruction assets under our benchmark, see Table 4.2. Comparing these results with our baseline gives a significant difference on all our assets. These results were expected since compute shaders are used to calculating large data sets, in this case meaning textures. Using threads for these compute shaders, a topic that is still undocumented, allowed for more exploration. During our thread study, see Section 4.2.3, we did not find any major improvements in performance except for the two-dimensional threads, visualized in Figure 4.5. We saw a decrease in performance with all our low-resolution SDF assets. Our high-resolution assets on the other hand did not see any performance changes. The origin of this spike is unknown. We did expect a better performance when using two thread groups for the calculation. As Table 4.5 and

Figure 4.5 displays, we did not meet our expectation. Further research would be needed to investigate this issue. Our texture format iteration resulted in significant improvements on all our assets, visualized in Table 4.6 and Figure 4.6. From this data we concluded that the texture format has a big impact and should not be neglected. We reduced the data needed by a quarter, as stated in Section 4.2.4, resulting in less memory consumption and a higher performance on the GPU. For the sphere tracing iteration, see Section 4.2.5, we moved the method to the GPU, which showed no significant improvement in performance, visualized by Figure 4.7. A reason for this could be that since we were only executing the sphere tracing algorithm once, with a maximum of 256 loops, it did not cause an overhead on the CPU.

The efficiency of our approach has reached and surpassed our minimum performance requirement. Figure 4.8 visualizes how each asset and resolution performs below our benchmark. Since our hardware is considered a mid-range setup, we can assume that this method will show the same if not better performance on high-end hardware. For the low-end hardware, see Section 4.2.7, we concluded that our method is only performing under the minimum performance requirement for the 64px^3 SDF assets, visualized in Figure 4.10. This means that we can still use our method on low-end hardware, with the correct limitations or level of detail. Which is a common practice in video games.

Based on this data it can be concluded that our proposed method shows the efficiency to be used in a real-time video game application.

5.3 Visual Comparison

Overall, our SDF destruction approach scored higher than the Voronoi method. This is clearly displayed in Figure 4.11, where we see that the mean of our method scored positive while the Voronoi method scored negative. A negative score does not mean that the statement is considered bad, rather that is less appealing compared to the other statements. The most preferred statement was 13, a Voronoi method, followed by four SDF statements. It could be said that certain methods are better suited for certain assets. However, this is just speculation, there is no indication that this is the case. Since four out of the five different assets favoured an SDF approach. From the Q-sorting results we concluded that the visual outcome of our proposed method is more visually appealing compared to the Voronoi method. We noticed that for the Voronoi statements all high level of detail assets scored higher in the Q-sorting. Whereas, the opposite was true for the SDF approach. Meaning while Voronoi relied on a high fracture count, our approach had no problem with a lower level of detail.

Figure 4.12 reveals that of all three subtraction functions, the most preferred function is the function that simulates the Voronoi fracturing by using a rotating cube. It is possibly due to the fact that we are so used to Voronoi fracturing, we associate this kind of style the most with destruction. This is not generally a bad thing; however, it does generalize destruction styles in video games. Our SDF approach can give more diversity and artistic possibilities, giving more character to destruction.

5.4 Limitations

While our method shows potential as a destruction method, we need to delve deeper and investigate how our approach performs on different in-game situations, assets, and hardware setups. Furthermore, we need to identify several limitations from our proposed destruction method.

The signed distance field destruction approach relies heavily on compute shaders to perform fast calculations. Even though it is an unlikely issue for future development, this limitation cannot be discarded. In the proposed method we created and modified our signed distance field texture with the use of compute shaders. Eliminating this progress would require a reevaluation of the iteration process. Furthermore, our data gathering did not include an extended scale behaviour analysis; to evaluate if different resolutions of SDF would have a linear or exponential impact on the performance.

The proposed method was also mainly focused on static rigid bodies. Destruction methods are rarely executed on soft bodies or skin meshes, nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that this too is a limitation of the proposed method. This can be partially resolved by further enhancing the SDF capabilities. Be aware that adding additional calculation in this progress will most likely increase the memory usage and have an impact on the performance.

Furthermore, applying of the damaging currently happens instantly. While this can be the case for certain events, a more 'evolution' of the damage would give it a more realistic feel. This could be partially resolved by introducing a tearing method into our proposed method. It would give the illusion of destruction happening over time, while visualizing the changes. Implementing a tearing effect will influence the performance of our proposed method, depending on how it was implemented and if the application is at runtime or predefined.

5.5 Future Possibilities

The prototype created during this research project could be used as a setup for further development. Although the prototype was not designed for an effortless user experience, the project does give a clear overview and starting point for any future research.

This destruction method introduces a new approach for destruction, providing the industry with a new tool to apply destruction for certain situations. We are essentially removing the pre-fracturing process of creating a destructible object and at the same time giving it a higher level of detail. This could benefit the development process tremendously. By reducing time and resources we are providing more creative possibilities in the art and game design process. This means that we are giving small budget games, that normally cannot afford to create different versions of destructible assets, the same opportunity to use destruction without increasing the budget.

Real-time applications that want to use or provide destruction on individual meshes would really benefit from this approach. This method does not change the workflow on how the asset creation is being done. Additionally, it does not create extra data. With this we mean that the application would not increase in size when adding this destruction method, which is currently the case when adding destructible assets. When using this method, one does need to be aware that this method runs on the GPU, so the platform should support compute shaders.

Other possible applications for this method could be a situation where the user needs a more hands-on or immersive experience regarding destruction; e.g., VR experiences, detailed destructions, in-game sculpting, art installations and other. New technologies such as Mesh Shaders or Nanite combined with the SDF Destruction approach would really push our method even further, providing non-destructible destruction on a triangle pixel detailed mesh.

It is worth mentioning that using our method translates into more accessibility without forcing a new workflow. This gives more opportunity for creativity, which can translate into new opportunities for this method. Or as John Lasseter would say, "The art challenges the technology, and the technology inspires the art." (John Lasseter, n.d.).

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Future Directions

We conclude our research by addressing our research questions, a reflection on the results from the previous chapter and what future research could be in the works.

6.1 Conclusion

This research topic explored how signed distance fields can benefit destruction on mesh data in a non-destructive way. The research question focused on how this method would be approached. The proposed way would be by creating a signed distance field of the destructible asset and executing all destruction operations on that SDF. We then start by rendering the asset with a traditional shader approach. However, we are also sampling from our SDF to examine if destruction took place and if so, we then visualize the destructed part by using the ray marching technique.

During our semi-structured interview, to determine our destruction criteria, we concluded that performance and aesthetic appeal were the most important topics considering a destruction method, since both have a direct impact on the end user. Which brought us to our two sub-questions; how efficient is this new approach and is the outcome visually appealing. The data of our performance test at the end of our iteration progress concludes that our efficiency surpassed our minimum performance requirement on both mid-range hardware as well as low-end hardware. Although it should be noted that for the low-end hardware only the 64^3 px SDF reached the minimum requirements. Regarding the visuals, we concluded that our method scored positive compared to the Voronoi destruction method, which proved its potential to be used as an alternative destruction method. During the visual study we used two different level of details for the SDF, one low-resolution of 64^3 px and a high-resolution SDF of 128^3 px. The expected result was that the higher resolution would be most preferred. However, surprisingly, the lower resolution was unanimously preferred.

Our proposed method shows the potential to be a legitimate destruction method. Although, further research is still needed to develop this method to apply to the current industry standards. This paper, with its accompanying prototype, is a good starting point for further research.

6.2 Future Directions

The proposed method could be used as a baseline for additional development. The collected data and the results can only be seen as an exploratory observation. During the

exploration study, we focused the prototype mainly on the Unity video game engine. This was primarily because of time and scope limitations during this research project. A more extensive evaluation on different video game engines and hardware could result in different results and should be investigated in future studies.

To improve comparison between different destruction methods, research could be conducted to propose a standardized destruction method to evaluate destruction techniques that would benefit future development. This would improve the comparison between different destruction techniques. The gathered data during the semi-structured interview could be a starting point for further research.

As mentioned in Section 5.5, this exploratory prototype could be expanded to include additional aspects of a destruction method, such as physics, rendering, VFX, and others. Which would push this method further towards a viable destruction solution to be used in the video game industry. Furthermore, it could resolve the current issues coming with the Voronoi approach, such as creating additional data. Along with the level of detail having to depend on the number of subdivisions. Other forms of interactive media could benefit from this approach as well. An example would be Virtual Reality applications or Art installations in need of a more immersive experience. Even film companies that are using real-time applications to develop their films could benefit from this method.

Chapter 7: Appendix A

A.1 Semi-Interview Questions

Question	Follow-up
Tell me about your carrier.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How long have you been working in the industry? - What is your “speciality” or field of interest? - How did you get in the video game industry? - What is your experience with destruction? - What game do you think of when we talk about destruction?
What are the steps you take for destruction?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there areas you want to improve, workflow wise? - What do you feel are the pros and cons of this approach? - Is this the most used method, and are you aware of other approached?
What is important for you when working with destruction?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If you would have to sum-up criteria? - Why is ... important? - Differences in film vs video game?
What do you think about these criteria, if we talk about destruction: control, performance, ease of use, ease of integration and quality?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there criteria missing? - Is one of these criteria overrated? - What’s the most important criteria, and which one is the less important one?
Would you be interested to test out a new approach?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can I contact you again for future developments?

A.2 Q-Sort Results

All the collected data from the Q-Sort.

[OneDrive Link to the Q-Sort Results and the grid example](#)

A.3 Iteration Results

All the collected data is expressed in ticks.

[OneDrive link to the Excel file for Iteration Results](#)

A.4 Video Results

The downloadable content contains all the captures videos used for the visual comparison study, a total of 16 videos.

[OneDrive Link to Videos](#)

A.5 Assets

These are the exact assets used for the continuous comparison study and the visual comparison study. All models are provided in a FBX format, and all SDF assets are provided in a Unity asset extension format.

[OneDrive Link to the Assets](#)

This package contains:

- Assets used during the continuous comparison study
- Signed Distance Fields of the assets
- Fractured assets for the visual comparison study

A.6 Source Code

Source code of the prototype.

[GitHub Link to the Source Code](#)

Chapter 8: Bibliography

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